

AN ECONOMIC ANALYSIS OF SUGARCANE CULTIVATION IN AHMEDNAGAR DISTRICT OF MAHARASHTRA

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(MS Received: 16.01.2023; MS Revised:17.02.2023; MS Accepted: 18.03.2023)

MS 2993

(RESEARCH PAPER IN AGRICULTURAL ECONOMICS & STATISTICS.)

Abstract

The study has based on primary data collected from 120 sugarcane growers spread over two blocks in Ahmednagar district from Karjat and Shrigonda tehsils of Maharashtra State in year 2021-2022 and estimated the cost and returns of sugarcane. Three villages were selected from each tehsils. Five farmer of each planting type i.e. Adsali, Pre-seasonal, Suru, and Ratoon sugarcane by simple random sampling technique. Thus, twenty farmers were selected from each village. The Study's main purpose was to estimate cost and returns in sugarcane production on different planting seasons in Ahmednagar district of Maharashtra States in India. Per hectare cost of cultivation of sugarcane at Cost 'C₃' was the highest in Adsali sugarcane i.e. Rs.297684.98 followed by pre-seasonal sugarcane Rs.272448.80, Suru sugarcane Rs.242232.10 and Ratoon sugarcane Rs.184240.82. Per hectare net returns of sugarcane at Cost 'C₃' was Rs.136668.73 in Adsali sugarcane followed by Pre-seasonal sugarcane Rs.97627.20, Suru sugarcane Rs.84435.90 and Ratoon sugarcane Rs.86431.18. The Input output ratio of sugarcane at Cost 'C₃' was 1.47 in Ratoon sugarcane followed by 1.46 in Adsali sugarcane, 1.36 in pre-seasonal sugarcane and 1.35 in Suru sugarcane.

Keywords – Sugarcane, cost, net returns, Input output ratio.

Introduction –

Sugarcane is a most important cash crop of India. Sugarcane provides raw material for the second largest agro-based industry after textile. Sugar industry is the Second largest agro based industry in rural India and act as focal point for socio- economic development.

Two distinct agro-climatic region of sugarcane cultivation in India viz., tropical and sub-tropical. Tropical region has about 45 per cent area and contributes 55 per cent of the total sugarcane production in the Country, Thus subtropical region accounts for 55 per cent area and shares 45 per cent of the total production. The tropical sugarcane region comprising the states of Maharashtra, Gujarat, Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka, Tamil Nadu, Kerala etc. accounted for 45 per cent of area and 55 per cent production whereas the sub-tropical region include the state of Uttar Pradesh, Bihar, Punjab, Haryana, Madhya Pradesh, Rajasthan, West Bengal, Assam, accounted for remaining 55 % area and 45 % production.

Sugarcane was cultivated in India on an area of 50.58 lakh hectares which harvested 430.50 million tonnes with a productivity 85.11 tonnes/ha in the year 2021-2022. The sugarcane cultivation and sugar industry in India plays a vital role towards socio-economic development of the rural areas by mobilizing rural resources and generating higher income and employment opportunities.

In Maharashtra Ahmednagar, Solapur, Kolhapur, Pune and Satara are the major sugarcane producing districts. This year in Maharashtra about 93 co-operative and 97 private sugar factories generating employment, electricity, ethanol production, bio-compost and number of other chemicals. Thus, sugarcane and sugar industry is the backbone for economic development of Maharashtra. The sugarcane crop plays a key role in the process of development as it generates income and employment. It is also noteworthy for being labour intensive, needing rapid investment, and giving high returns as compared to other crops and its significant contribution to the country's as well as the state economics.

Maharashtra ranks second in the list of largest sugarcane producing state in India. Maharashtra rank second in area (14.88 lakh hectare) and production (132.03 million tonnes) of sugarcane and rank third in sugarcane productivity (88.00 tonnes/ha) during the year 2021-2022.

Materials and Methods

The present study on yield gap analysis of sugarcane crop was purposively undertaken in Ahmednagar district of Maharashtra State. Two tehsils viz. Karjat and Shrigonda having maximum area under sugarcane cultivation were selected purposively for the study. In all six villages i.e. three villages each from Karjat and Shrigonda tehsils, were selected randomly.

The list of sugarcane growers from the selected villages were obtained from the revenue records maintained at selected villages and then categorized into four groups according to planting types of sugarcane. Five farmers of each type i.e. Adsali, Suru, Pre-seasonal, and Ratoon sugarcane were selected separately from each village from both the tehsils by simple random sampling technique. Thus, 20 farmers were selected from each village. In all 120 sugarcane growers comprising 30 farmers from each planting type of sugarcane were selected separately for the present study. The primary data were collected from sample sugarcane growers by the survey method.

The field level data on the use of various inputs viz. seed, manures, fertilizers, number of irrigation, labour use pattern and yield obtained from sugarcane cultivation, constraints in the use of inputs etc. and general information of sample cultivators, such as family composition, land utilization, cropping pattern and assets position of the farmers etc. were collected from the sample sugarcane growers. The information on research station yield and yield of field level demonstration plot were obtained from the central research station Padegaon (M.S). The data were collected for the crop harvested in the year 2021-2022.

Economics of sugarcane production

Economics of sugarcane production was worked out by using standard cost concepts.

i) COST A₁

It is the actual paid out cost incurred by the cultivator. This cost comprise of the expenditure incurred by the farmers in cash as well as kind for the cultivation of Sugarcane in respect of following items.

1. Hired human labour
2. Hired and Owned bullock labour
3. Machinery charges.
4. Seed or Planting material (both farm produce and purchased)
5. Manure
6. Fertilizers
7. Plant Protection
8. Irrigation charges
9. Depreciation on implements and farm building.
10. Land revenue and other taxes
11. Interest on working capital.

ii) COST A₂

Cost A₁+ Rent paid for leased-in land.

iii) COST B₁

Cost A₁+ interest value of owned fixed capital assets (excluding land)

iv) COST B₂

Cost B₁ + Rental value of owned land

v) COST C₁

Cost B₁ + imputed value of family labour

vi) COST C₂

Cost B₂ + imputed value of family labour

vii) COST C₃

Cost C₂ + 10 % of Cost C₂

GROSS AND NET RETURNS

Gross Returns : Returns obtained from the sale of crops output i.e. main Produce and by-produce

Net Returns : Net returns were computed at different cost concept i.e. Cost A₁, Cost A₂, Cost B₁, Cost B₂, Cost C₁, Cost C₂, and Cost C₃ by deducting respective cost from the gross returns.

Input - Output Ratio

The input-output ratio relationship was worked out on the basis of standard cost concepts.

a. Input – output ratio at Cost A₁

$$\text{Input – Output Ratio} = \frac{\text{Gross Income}}{\text{Cost A}_1}$$

b. Input – Output Ratio at Cost A₂

$$\text{Input – Output Ratio} = \frac{\text{Gross Income}}{\text{Cost A}_2}$$

c. Input – Output Ratio at Cost B₁

$$\text{Input – Output Ratio} = \frac{\text{Gross Income}}{\text{Cost B}_1}$$

e. Input – Output Ratio at Cost C₁

$$\text{Input – Output Ratio} = \frac{\text{Gross Income}}{\text{Cost C}_1}$$

f. Input – Output Ratio at Cost C₂

$$\text{Input – Output Ratio} = \frac{\text{Gross Income}}{\text{Cost C}_2}$$

g. Input – Output Ratio at Cost C₃

$$\text{Input – Output Ratio} = \frac{\text{Gross Income}}{\text{Cost C}_3}$$

Results and Discussion

The Cost of cultivation is helpful for crop planning therefore in order to know the cost and profitability, the cost of cultivation of sugarcane for Adsali, Pre-seasonal, Suru, Ratoon planting type of farmers was worked out.

Per hectare Physical input utilization for sugarcane

The per hectare physical input utilization for sugarcane cultivation is given in Table 1. The, total human labour were highest in adsali sugarcane cultivation i.e. 168.01 days, of which 96.37 days were male labour, 71.64 days were female labour and lowest in ratoon sugarcane cultivation which were 127.74 days, among these 71.90 days were male labour and 55.84 days were female labour. Per hectare machine power used were highest in Adsali Sugarcane cultivation i.e. 32.49 hours and lowest in ratoon sugarcane 15.86 hours. Across the planting type i.e. Adsali, Pre-seasonal, Suru, and Ratoon the use of bullock labour in sugarcane was 3.86, 3.43, 2.44, and 2.88 days respectively.

The per hectare quantity of planting materials used were highest in Adsali Sugarcane i.e. 5.85 tonnes followed by pre-seasonal and Ratoon sugarcane cultivation was 5.52 and 5.15 tonnes. In Sugarcane cultivation manure are the important input, it is used in large quantity in Adsali, pre-seasonal, Suru, and Ratoon cultivation it was 22.62, 22.03, 18.06, and 17.89 tonnes/ha respectively. The per hectare fertilizer use is highest in Adsali sugarcane, i.e. 358.27 kg of N, 155.71 kg of P and 139.10 kg of K and lowest fertilizer are used in Suru sugarcane cultivation. It was 224.77 kg of N, 103.81 kg of P and 96.26 kg of K. The use of plant protection is highest in Adsali Sugarcane cultivation (8.46 litre) followed by pre-seasonal Sugarcane cultivation (6.96 litre) and Suru and ratoon sugarcane cultivation 6.57 and 6.14 litre/ha respectively.

Per hectare cost of cultivation of sugarcane

The item wise and planting type wise per hectare cost of cultivation of sugarcane is presented in Table.2. It is observed from Table 2 that total cost of cultivation (Cost C₃) is highest in adsali sugarcane was worked out to be Rs.297684.98 and lowest in Ratoon Sugarcane cultivation Rs.184240.82, in pre-seasonal and suru sugarcane cultivation total cost of cultivation was worked out to Rs.272448.80 and Rs.242232.10 respectively. In adsali Sugarcane of total cost of cultivation (cost C₃), share of cost A₁ was 57.07 per cent and cost B₁ and cost B₂ was 59.50 and 83.75 per cent while in Ratoon sugarcane, total cost of cultivation (Cost C₃), was worked out to be Rs. 184240.82 of which share of cost A₁ was 54.24 per cent and and cost B₁ and cost B₂ 56.58 and 81.06 per cent respectively. It was observed from the result that cost A₁ was highest in Adsali sugarcane cultivation i.e. Rs.169887.12 and it was minimum in Ratoon Sugarcane i.e. Rs.99935.47.

In adsali Sugarcane, out of the total cost the most expensive item was rental value of land (24.25%), followed by hired human labour (10.59%), Manure (9.88%), planting materials (8.85%), fertilizer (6.61%), machine charges (6.55%), interest on working capital (6.04%), irrigation charges (3.59 %), Plant Protection (2.59%), Interest on fixed capital (2.43 %), bullock labour (0.78 %), depreciation (0.61%) and land revenue (0.07%).

In ratoon Sugarcane crop, out of the total cost the most expensive item was rental value of land (24.38%), followed by hired human labour (11.83%), Manure (12.62%), fertilizer (7.56 %), machine charges (5.16%), interest on working capital (5.65%), irrigation charges (4.70%), Plant Protection (2.96%), Interest on fixed capital (2.44%), depreciation (1.42%), bullock labour (0.94) and land revenue (0.11%).

The results revealed that, total cost of cultivation i.e Cost C₃ is highest in Adsali sugarcane cultivation (Rs.297684.98) followed by pre-seasonal (Rs.272448.80), Suru (Rs.242232.10) and Ratoon sugarcane cultivation (Rs.184240.82). The sugarcane grower maximum capital utilized in hired labour, followed by manure, fertilizer, planting materials, machine power, plant protection and irrigation.

Table.1. Per hectare physical input utilization for sugarcane (per ha)

Sr. No	Input	Unit	Planting type			
			Adsali	Preseasonal	Suru	Ratoon
1	Total Human Labour					
	Male	Days	96.37	91.52	83.20	71.90
	Female	Days	71.64	65.65	59.49	55.84
			168.01	157.17	142.69	127.74
2	Hired Human Labour					
	Male	Days	54.58	53.47	47.00	36.40
	Female	Days	48.58	44.90	38.83	36.09
3	Bullock labour	Days	3.86	3.43	2.44	2.88
4	Machine power	Hours	32.49	31.25	31.56	15.86
5	Manures	Tonnes	22.62	22.03	18.06	17.89
6	Planting materials	Tonnes	5.85	5.52	5.15	-
7	Fertilizers					
	N	Kg	358.27	311.25	224.77	232.70
	P	Kg	155.71	152.87	103.81	109.65
	K	Kg	139.10	137.99	96.26	107.63
8	Micronutrients		5.04	4.13	2.88	3.58
	Plant protection	Litre	8.46	6.96	6.57	6.14
9	Family Labour					
	Male	Days	41.79	38.05	36.20	35.50
	Female	Days	23.06	20.75	20.66	19.75
10	Yield					
	Main produce	Tonnes	152.01	129.13	114.31	94.16
	By produce	Tonnes	10.91	10.64	8.25	8.78

Table.2. Per hectare cost of cultivation of sugarcane (Rs/ha)

S. N.	Item	Planting Type			
		Adsali	Preseasonal	Suru	Ratoon
1	Hired Human labour				
	Male	21831.35 (7.33)	21388.13 (7.85)	18800.00 (7.76)	14561.11 (7.91)
	Female	9716.59 (3.26)	8980.71 (3.30)	7765.56 (3.21)	7218.33 (3.92)
	Subtotal	31547.94 (10.59)	30368.84 (11.15)	26565.56 (10.97)	21779.44 (11.83)
2	Bullock Labour	2315.12 (0.78)	2056.07 (0.75)	1465.00 (0.60)	1726.67 (0.94)
3	Machine Charges	19493.45 (6.55)	18753.63 (6.88)	18933.33 (7.82)	9515.00 (5.16)
4	Manures	29408.24 (9.88)	28635.08 (10.51)	23483.05 (9.69)	23251.94 (12.62)
5	Planting Materials	26339.82 (8.85)	24820.71 (9.11)	23182.50 (9.57)	0
6	Fertilizers				
	N	4595.15 (1.54)	3992.18 (1.47)	2882.87 (1.19)	2984.55 (1.62)
	P	10607.84 (3.56)	10413.95 (3.82)	7071.98 (2.92)	7469.83 (4.05)
	K	4497.79 (1.51)	4461.78 (1.64)	3112.62 (1.28)	3480.14 (1.89)
	Subtotal	19700.78 (6.61)	18867.91 (6.93)	13067.47 (5.39)	13934.52 (7.56)
7	Micro Nutrients	554.95 (0.19)	454.46 (0.17)	317.47 (0.13)	394.17 (0.21)

8	Irrigation Charges	10679.08 (3.59)	9775.91 (3.59)	9688.61 (4.00)	8656.67 (4.70)
9	Plant Protection	7720.33 (2.59)	6060.95 (2.22)	5988.58 (2.47)	5459.25 (2.96)
10	Incidental Charges	1194.79 (0.40)	1082.24 (0.40)	1072.92 (0.44)	1124.81 (0.61)
11	Repairing Charges	937.83 (0.32)	888.56 (0.33)	908.72 (0.38)	873.28 (0.47)
12	Working Capital (1 to 11)	149892.33 (50.35)	141764.37 (52.04)	124673.20 (51.46)	86715.75 (47.06)
13	Int. on working Capital	17987.08 (6.04)	17011.72 (6.24)	14960.78 (6.18)	10405.89 (5.65)
14	Depreciation	1805.00 (0.61)	1705.62 (0.63)	2097.15 (0.87)	2617.05 (1.42)
15	Land Revenue	202.71 (0.07)	201.49 (0.07)	198.19 (0.08)	196.78 (0.11)
16	Cost A₁	169887.12 (57.07)	160683.20 (58.98)	141929.33 (58.59)	99935.47 (54.24)
17	Rental value of leased land	0	0	0	0
18	Cost A₂	169887.12 (57.07)	160683.20 (58.98)	141929.33 (58.59)	99935.47 (54.24)
19	Int. on Fixed Capital @ 10%	7218.96 (2.43)	6147.78 (2.26)	5424.65 (2.24)	4491.52 (2.44)
20	Cost B₁	177106.08 (59.50)	166830.98 (61.24)	147353.98 (60.83)	104426.99 (56.68)
21	Rental value of land	72189.58 (24.25)	61477.84 (22.56)	54246.47 (22.39)	44915.22 (24.25)
22	Cost B₂	249295.66 (83.75)	228308.83 (83.80)	201600.45 (83.22)	149342.21 (81.06)
23	Family Human Labour				
	Male	16714.44 (5.61)	15221.71 (5.59)	14478.89 (5.98)	14200.00 (7.71)
	Female	4612.61 (1.55)	4150.19 (1.52)	4131.67 (1.71)	3949.44 (2.14)
	Subtotal	21327.05 (7.16)	19371.90 (7.11)	18610.56 (7.69)	18149.44 (9.85)
24	Cost C₁	198433.13 (66.66)	186202.88 (68.35)	165964.53 (68.52)	122576.43 (66.53)
25	Cost C₂	270622.71 (90.91)	247680.73 (90.91)	220211.00 (90.91)	167491.65 (90.91)
27	10 % of C ₂	27062.27 (9.09)	24768.07 (9.09)	22021.10 (9.09)	16749.17 (9.09)
27	Cost C₃	297684.98 (100.00)	272448.80 (100.00)	242232.10 (100.00)	184240.82 (100.00)
28	Main Produce	425628.00	361564.00	320068.00	263648.00
29	By produce	8725.71	8512	6600.00	7024.00
30	Value of Total Produce	434353.71	370076.00	326668.00	270672.00
31	per tonne Cost of Production	1722.89	1852.15	1868.70	1704.20

Per hectare cost, returns, and profitability from sugarcane:

The per hectare cost, returns, and profitability of sugarcane cultivation was worked out as per standard cost concept, and is presented in table

3. **Table.3. Per hectare cost, returns, and profitability from Sugarcane**

(Rs/ha)

S.N.	Particulars	Planting type			
		Adsali	Preseasonal	Suru	Ratoon
1	Main Produce				
	Quantity (Tonne/ha)	152.01	129.13	114.31	94.16
	Price (Rs/Tonne)	2800	2800	2800	2800
	Returns(Rs)	425628.00	361564	320068.00	263648.00
2	By- Produce				
	Quantity (Tonne/ha)	10.91	10.64	8.25	8.78
	Price (Rs /Tonne)	800	800	800	800

	Returns(Rs)	8725.71	8512.00	6600.00	7024.00
3	Gross Returns (Rs)	434353.71	370076.00	326668.00	270672.00
4	Cost of Cultivation at				
	Cost A ₁	169887.12	160683.20	141929.33	99935.47
	Cost A ₂	169887.12	160683.20	475197.33	99935.47
	Cost B ₁	177106.08	166830.98	147353.98	104426.99
	Cost B ₂	249295.66	228308.83	201600.44	149342.21
	Cost C ₁	198433.13	186202.88	165964.53	122576.43
	Cost C ₂	270622.71	247680.73	220211.00	167491.65
	Cost C ₃	297684.98	272448.80	242232.10	184240.82
5	Net Returns at				
	Cost A ₁	264466.59	209392.80	184738.67	170736.53
	Cost A ₂	264466.59	209392.80	184738.67	170736.53
	Cost B ₁	257247.63	203245.02	179314.02	166245.00
	Cost B ₂	185058.05	141767.17	125067.55	121329.79
	Cost C ₁	235920.58	183873.12	160703.47	148095.57
	Cost C ₂	163731.00	122395.27	106457.00	103180.35
	Cost C ₃	136668.73	97627.20	84435.90	86431.18
6	Input-Output Ratio at				
	Cost A ₁	2.56	2.30	2.30	2.71
	Cost A ₂	2.56	2.30	2.30	2.71
	Cost B ₁	2.45	2.22	2.22	2.59
	Cost B ₂	1.74	1.62	1.62	1.81
	Cost C ₁	2.19	1.99	1.97	2.21
	Cost C ₂	1.61	1.49	1.48	1.62
	Cost C ₃	1.46	1.36	1.35	1.47

It is revealed from the table 3 that, the price realized by producer was Rs.2800/tonne for main produce and Rs.800/tonne for by produce, for Adsali, pre-seasonal, Suru, Ratoon sugarcane crop respectively. The main produce from the sugarcane was 152.01, 129.13, 114.31 and 94.16 tonnes/ha respectively and by-produce was 10.91, 10.64, 8.25 and 8.78 tonnes/ha from adsali, preseasonal, suru, and ratoon sugarcane respectively. The net returns from main produce were Rs.425628, Rs.361564, Rs.320068, Rs.263648 and by-produce was Rs.8725.71, Rs.8512.00, Rs.6600.00, and Rs.7024.00. The Gross return from sugarcane at Cost 'C₃' was Rs.434353.71, Rs.370076.00, Rs.326668.00, and Rs.270672.00 from adsali, preseasonal, suru and ratoon planting type of sugarcane. Where as the cost of cultivation at C₃ of these planting types have been estimated to be Rs.297684.98, Rs.272448.80, Rs.242232.10, and Rs.184240.82.

The per hectare net returns at Cost C₃ received by Adsali, pre-seasonal, Suru, and Ratoon sugarcane was Rs.136668.73, Rs.97627.20, Rs.84435.90 and Rs.86431.18. The Benefit-Cost ratio at cost C₃ for Adsali, Pre-seasonal, Suru, and Ratoon sugarcane was 1.46, 1.36, 1.35, and 1.47 respectively. This analysis indicated that sugarcane crop all season that is adsali, preseasonal, suru and ratoon was profitable.

Summary

Ahmednagar district being one of the major sugarcane growing district from western Maharashtra, was selected purposively for the present investigation.

Per hectare cost 'A₁' was highest in adsali planting type sugarcane i.e Rs.169887.12 followed by preseasonal planting type sugarcane i.e Rs.160683.20, Suru planting type sugarcane i.e Rs.141929.33 and ratoon planting type sugarcane i.e Rs.99935.47 respectively.

The per hectare total cost of cultivation of sugarcane i.e cost 'C₃' was highest in the Adsali planting type sugarcane (Rs.297684.98) followed by pre-seasonal (Rs.272448.80), Suru (Rs.242232.10) and Ratoon (Rs.184240.82).

The Input output ratio of sugarcane cultivation at cost 'C₃' was higher in Ratoon planting type sugarcane (1.47) followed by Adsali (1.46), Pre-seasonal (1.36) and Suru (1.35) sugarcane.

Conclusions

1. The sugarcane growers employed relatively higher quantity of resources for the production of Adsali followed by pre-seasonal, Suru, and Ratoon sugarcane.
2. The productivity of Adsali sugarcane was also higher than other types of sugarcane.
3. Per hectare cost of cultivation of sugarcane at cost C₃ was highest in the Adsali sugarcane i.e Rs.297684.98 followed by pre-seasonal sugarcane Rs.272448.80, Suru sugarcane Rs.242232.10 and ratoon sugarcane Rs.184240.82.
4. The Input output ratio of sugarcane cultivation at cost C₃ was 1.46 in Adsali sugarcane, 1.36 in Pre-seasonal sugarcane, 1.35 in Suru Sugarcane, and 1.47 in Ratoon sugarcane.
5. Out of the four planting type of sugarcane ratoon and adsali planting type sugarcane was profitable.

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